

1 **Calcium sulphate biomineralisation: artefact of sample preparation?**

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3 **Andreu Cera^{1,2*}, Cristóbal Verdugo-Escamilla³, Juan A. Marín⁴, Sara Palacio²**

4 ¹ Centro de Ecología Aplicada Prof. Baeta Neves (CEABN-InBIO), Instituto Superior de
5 Agronomia, Universidade de Lisboa, Tapada da Ajuda, 1349-017, Lisboa, Portugal

6 ² Departamento Biodiversidad y Restauración, Instituto Pirenaico de Ecología, Consejo
7 Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Avda. Nuestra Señora de la Victoria 14, 22700 Jaca,
8 Spain

9 ³ Laboratorio de Estudios Cristalográficos, IACT, CSIC-Universidad de Granada, Avda. de las
10 Palmeras 4, 18100 Armilla, Spain

11 ⁴ Departamento de Pomología, Estación Experimental de Aula Dei CSIC, Av. Montañana 1005,
12 50059 Zaragoza, Spain

13
14 Author for correspondence:

15 Andreu Cera

16 Email: andreucera@isa.ulisboa.pt

18 **Abstract**

19 Calcium biomineralisation is widely documented in plants. However, crystallisation of Ca-
20 sulphate-containing minerals is closely related to water content, and sample processing, such
21 as drying, alters the water balance of plant tissues. We hypothesised that common sample
22 processing practices may favour the formation of crystals, leading to spurious crystallisation
23 not observed in unaltered plant tissues. We selected three species (*Ononis tridentata*,
24 *Helianthemum squamatum*, *Gypsophila struthium*) with reported gypsum biomineralisation.
25 We used X-ray diffractometry on fresh intact or sliced leaves, and on the same leaves processed
26 by subsequent drying, to address whether sample processing alters crystal formation. Ca-
27 sulphate crystals were detected in dry samples of all species but not in fresh intact samples. Ca-
28 sulphate crystallisation occurred in some cut fresh samples, although the accumulation greatly
29 increased after drying. In addition, *G. struthium* exhibited Ca-oxalate crystals in both fresh and

30 dry treatments, with a tendency for greater accumulation in dry treatments. Our results
31 demonstrate that the Ca-sulphate crystals observed by X-ray diffractometry in these species are
32 artefacts caused by common sample processing practices, such as excessive drying and slicing
33 samples. We encourage future studies on the biomineral potential of plants to avoid the use of
34 procedures that alter the water balance of tissues.

35

36 **Key-words:** biomineralisation, calcium, gypsum, X-ray diffractometry, plant-soil interactions,
37 Sulphur

38

39 **1-INTRODUCTION**

40 The interaction of plants with soils is an important field in plant sciences, with major consequences
41 on ecosystem functioning and plant productivity. Plants mainly absorb mineral nutrients from the soil.
42 Sometimes, these mineral nutrients are found in concentrations greater than the plant requirements
43 (Kabata-Pendias 2010), and plants must manage uptake and accumulation to avoid metabolic
44 imbalances in cells (Lambers and Oliveira 2019). Plants can prevent the acquisition of such excess
45 nutrients by using roots as a nutritional barrier, and/or by tolerating them in aboveground parts (Tran et
46 al. 2020; Lux et al. 2021), for example by forming biominerals (He et al., 2014).

47 Biomineralisation has been documented in plants for several centuries as the accumulation of
48 calcium (Ca) and silica (Si) minerals in plant tissues (Franceschi and Nakata 2005; Bauer et al. 2011;
49 He et al. 2014). Ca precipitation in different mineral forms is widespread across plant lineages (He *et*
50 *al.*, 2012). Ca oxalate is the most documented Ca mineral biomineralised by plants. It is found in more
51 than 215 plant families (Brown et al. 2013). However, other Ca minerals containing carbonate or
52 sulphate have also been reported inside plant tissues (He et al. 2015). The evolutionary driving force for
53 Ca mineralisation may be primarily the prevention of Ca ion accumulation inside the cell when Ca
54 acquisition surpasses plant requirements (Bauer et al. 2011). Although other functions such as Ca
55 storage, defence against herbivory, or metal detoxification have been suggested for Ca biomineralisation
56 in plants (Franceschi and Nakata 2005; He et al. 2014), experimental evidence is still limited (Paiva

57 2019, 2021; Karabourniotis et al. 2020). Elucidating the processes behind the formation of mineral
58 deposits in plants is crucial to understand plant-soil interactions, and has a huge impact on our
59 understanding of plant functioning.

60 Ca-sulphate biomineralisation has been reported in plants growing worldwide. Depending on the
61 conditions (e.g. saturation state, temperature, pressure, and water activity), this group of evaporite
62 minerals can precipitate to form anhydrite (CaSO_4), bassanite ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 1/2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) or gypsum
63 ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (Van Driessche et al. 2017). Gypsum biomineralisation is the most commonly reported
64 and is usually associated with plants growing on gypsum soils (Moore et al. 2014; Palacio et al. 2014;
65 Muller et al. 2017; Kayabaş and Yildirim 2021). However, gypsum biomineralisation has also been
66 observed in *Acacia* spp. (He et al. 2015), *Sarcoconia carinata* (Rufo et al. 2021) and the lichen *Ramalina*
67 *lacera* (Garty et al. 2002) growing off gypsum soils. Although no records have been found for anhydrite
68 formation in plant tissues, bassanite has been observed in the wood of *Tamarix* sp. trees (Weiner et al.
69 2021).

70 Crystallisation is the organised precipitation of solids from a solution or gas, and is therefore tightly
71 related to the liquid water content under normal conditions (101.3KPa, 20°C in plants). For example,
72 gypsum crystallises when the concentration of Ca-sulphate in solution surpasses $2.23 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (Van
73 Driessche et al. 2017). Therefore, osmotic conditions inside plant tissues may be key for biomineral
74 precipitation. Most procedures commonly used to analyse plant biomineralisation involve drying or
75 altering the osmotic conditions in plant tissues and, consequently, may affect crystal formation. For
76 example, SEM microscopy involves sectioning plant tissues (which damages cells and consequently
77 alters the osmotic conditions inside them) and drying or dehydrating (often by critical point drying with
78 CO_2) (He et al. 2012). FTIR spectroscopy, a technique widely used to study mineral components in
79 plants (Palacio et al. 2014), requires drying and milling plant tissues, completely altering the osmotic
80 conditions and water content of samples. Tissue sectioning, drying, dehydration and milling could
81 significantly promote the formation of Ca-sulphate biocrystals, leading to artefactual crystal formation,
82 with important consequences for subsequent physiological and ecological interpretations.

83 Conversely, X-ray diffraction (XRD) is a widely used procedure in crystallographic studies
84 (Criado-Reyes et al. 2023). This technique can be applied directly to unaltered fresh tissues, hence

85 providing information on the presence of mineral crystals in vivo. The application of this technique to
86 plant samples could provide robust information on the presence of Ca-sulphate biominerals in plants.
87 However, to our knowledge, no studies have evaluated the presence of Ca-sulphate biominerals in plants
88 without altering the cell structure to date.

89 The aim of this study was to evaluate Ca-sulphate biomineralisation in three common species for
90 which gypsum biomineralisation has been reported. We used XRD in fresh and dried samples and in
91 entire or sliced samples, to address whether sample processing techniques widely used in
92 biomineralisation studies alter the formation of crystals.

93

94 **2-MATERIAL AND METHODS**

95 **2.1-Study species**

96 We selected three species with previously reported gypsum mineralisation and high S
97 concentration in leaves (Palacio et al. 2014): *Gypsophila struthium* L., *Helianthemum squamatum* Pers.
98 and *Ononis tridentata* L (Figure 1). All are sub-shrubs and representative of the dominant vegetation in
99 gypsum ecosystems of Spain (Moore et al. 2014).

100

101 **2.2- Plant collection**

102 We collected specimens in gypsum outcrops in south-eastern Spain. *H. squamatum* and *O.*
103 *tridentata* were collected in Escúzar (Granada, Spain, 37°03'29.1"N 3°45'48.5"W; 930 m a.s.l.), whereas
104 specimens of *G. struthium* were collected in Villanueva de las Torres (Granada, Spain, 37°30'35.0"N
105 3°06'03.3"W; 750 m a.s.l.). All collections were made on 3 July 2022.

106 Five specimens of each species were collected. We chose individuals located at least two meters
107 apart from each other. Selected individuals were healthy adult plants with their foliage exposed to full
108 sunlight. We collected complete branches using secateurs and placed them individually in polyethylene
109 bags and transported them to the laboratory, where plants were processed immediately.

110

111 **2.3-Sample processing**

112 At the laboratory, branches were partly immersed in a bucket of tap water, and a 10-cm segment
113 was cut off the most proximal part of the main stem of each branch under water to remove potential
114 embolized xylem prior to branch re-hydration. After cutting off the basal segment of the stem, branches
115 were immediately transferred to falcon tubes filled with tap water by submerging the stems. Branches
116 were stored in the refrigerator at 4°C overnight, covered with a polyethylene plastic bag previously
117 sprayed with tap water, to obtain plant samples at full hydration (Palacio et al. 2008).

118 Two sample processing treatments were evaluated: entire leaves or leaves cut into transverse
119 sections. To observe entire leaves, a subsample of leaves (including petioles) was separated from each
120 fragment and weighed on a precision scale (42 g/0.00001 g, MS105DU, Mettler Toledo). Senescent or
121 damaged leaves were avoided. We separated five leaves of each individual for *G. struthium*, three for
122 *H. squamatum* and two for *O. tridentata*. The amount of leaves was chosen according to the leaf size of
123 each species and that of the slide for X-ray diffraction observation. Leaves were mounted on the slide
124 between two sheets of Mylar polyester film and sprayed slightly with tap water to keep them moist under
125 XRD observation. Observations were made the next morning after plant collection in groups of three
126 specimens, one of each species, changing the order each time. After XRD observation, samples were
127 dismounted, dried to a constant weight at 50°C for one week, weighed, and analysed again in the
128 diffractometer. To study sectioned leaves, a subsample of leaves was separated and cut transversely with
129 a razor blade into fragments approximately 2 mm wide. We separated the same number of leaves for
130 each species, as described for entire leaves. Cut fragments were mounted on a slide between two sheets
131 of Mylar polyester film and sprayed slightly with tap water. After XRD observation, they were dried
132 and analysed as described for entire leaves.

133

134 **2.4-X-ray diffraction analyses**

135 Powder X-ray diffraction data were collected using a Bruker D8 Advance Varío diffractometer
136 (Bruker-AXS) equipped with a LYNXEYE detector, primary Ge (111) monochromator, and Cu-K α 1
137 radiation (1.5406 Å). Diffractograms were acquired in transmission mode, at 40 kV acceleration voltage
138 and 40 mA current, with 2 θ scans spanning from 5 to 80° with a 2 θ step of 0.02° s⁻¹. The observation
139 time for each sample was 20 min. The detection limit of the diffractometer used depends on many

140 variables and can reach a detection of 0.1% of the dry weight of the samples. DIFFRAC.EVA software
141 (version 4.2) with the ICDD PDF-4+ (2021) database was used for phase identification.

142

143 **3-RESULTS**

144 Ca-sulphate crystals were detected in dried samples of all species but not in fresh intact samples.
145 Fresh samples had $72.02 \pm 1.26\%$ water content for *Gypsophila struthium*, $77.55 \pm 0.53\%$ for *Ononis*
146 *tridentata* and $70.87 \pm 2.08\%$ for *Helianthemum squamatum*. None of the specimens analysed showed
147 gypsum crystals in fresh entire leaves (Figure 2, see other replicates of diffractograms in Supplementary
148 Files). However, in all specimens of *H. squamatum* and *O. tridentata* and in one replicate of *G.*
149 *hispanica*, gypsum crystals were recorded on the same samples after drying. Some specimens of *H.*
150 *squamatum* and *O. tridentata* also showed bassanite ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 1/2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) crystals after drying (Figure
151 2B,C). All specimens of *G. struthium* had Ca-oxalate crystals (whewellite) either on fresh and dried
152 treatments, with a trend of higher accumulation in dried treatments (Figure 2A).

153 Ca-sulphate crystallisation occurred in some cut samples, either in fresh or dried samples (Figure
154 3, see other replicates of diffractograms in Supplementary Files). All specimens of *O. tridentata* had
155 gypsum crystals in fresh cut samples, but the accumulation increased greatly after drying. Some
156 replicates of *H. squamatum* showed weak peaks of gypsum crystals in fresh-cut samples, and all
157 replicates showed strong peaks in dry-cut samples. Specimens of *G. struthium* had no gypsum crystals
158 in fresh-cut samples, but these were formed in two specimens after drying. Ca-oxalate crystals were
159 always present in fresh-cut leaves of *G. struthium* and after drying, but dried samples showed a greater
160 accumulation than fresh ones.

161

162 **4-DISCUSSION**

163 Drying samples to a constant weight at 50°C for one week (a common practice in plant science)
164 was the main treatment altering the formation of Ca-sulphate crystals in our study, because this treatment
165 removed all water in leaves. Target species have high concentrations of Ca and sulphate in leaves
166 (Moore et al. 2014), and drying led to the precipitation of Ca-sulphate in the form of crystals. We mainly

167 observed gypsum crystal formation because this is the stable phase of Ca-sulphate under 40°C, whereas
168 anhydrite is the stable phase over 130°C, and bassanite is a transition phase (Van Driessche et al. 2017).
169 Consequently, it is not surprising that we observed bassanite crystallisation in *Helianthemum*
170 *squamatum* and *Ononis tridentata* samples dried at 50°C. Slicing leaves also slightly promoted the
171 formation of crystals because cutting leaf tissues altered the leaf water balance. The effect of slicing was
172 clearly observed in *O. tridentata* as this species has more succulent leaves and higher water content than
173 *H. squamatum* and *G. struthium* (pers. observ.). In addition, in the sole species that formed Ca-OX
174 crystals, crystals were also observed in fresh leaves, confirming biomineralisation, but the amount of
175 Ca-OX crystals recorded increased remarkably after both processing treatments. This result is not
176 surprising since Ca-OX is less soluble ($0.00067 \text{ g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ at 20°C) than Ca-sulphate, which explains its
177 presence in intact leaves, but it also shows that it is a more sensitive mineral to water content.

178 These results have implications for the understanding of plant functioning. We have demonstrated
179 that biomineralisation is tightly linked to leaf water content. This consideration is especially important
180 when dealing with minerals with moderate or high solubility, as is the case with Ca-sulphate crystals.
181 Therefore, any method altering foliar water balance may lead to spurious crystal formation, resulting in
182 misleading or inaccurate conclusions about plant function. For example, the accumulation of Ca-
183 sulphate in gypsum plants was previously interpreted as a way for plants to sequester excess Ca and
184 sulphates in the form of biocrystals (He et al. 2014; Palacio et al. 2014), similar to the role of Ca-OX
185 under conditions of excess Ca (He et al. 2014). Further, the presence of Ca-sulphate biominerals has
186 also been interpreted to play a role in preventing herbivory (Palacio et al. 2014). In contrast, our results
187 indicate that the plants studied accumulated Ca-sulphates inside plant tissues at oversaturation. These
188 plants probably use other elements, such as magnesium, which has also been found to accumulate
189 profusely in gypsum plants (Muller et al. 2017) to reduce the nucleation and growth kinetics of Ca-
190 sulphate crystals (Rabizadeh et al. 2017). This finding opens the window to new interpretations about
191 the role of Ca-sulphate accumulation in plants, such as the case of plant specialisation to gypsum soils
192 (Cera et al. 2023), where gypsum endemics would accumulate Ca-sulphate in oversaturation and not
193 biomineralise.

194

195 **5-CONCLUSIONS**

196 In conclusion, this communication highlights certain crucial aspects to be considered for future
197 studies on plant biomineralisation. Future studies on the biomineral potential of plants should avoid the
198 use of procedures that alter the water balance of plant tissues, such as drying, cutting, slicing, fixation
199 in formalin-acetic acid, ethanol or acetone, or cell lysis. Future studies should also reduce the time
200 elapsed between plant collection and analysis, as it may modify the water balance of plant tissues. The
201 use of non-invasive techniques such as X-ray diffractometry or X-ray computed tomography is
202 recommended over optic, transmission or scanning microscopy (Matsushima et al. 2012). The cryo-
203 preparation of samples and subsequent observation with low-temperature SEM or low vacuum
204 environmental SEM in the presence of water vapour may be appropriate, although its potential
205 interference with crystal formation should be further investigated. Histological techniques that do not
206 involve cutting of tissues, such as diaphanisation and sodium hypochlorite clearing, should also be tested
207 to observe crystals in plant organs. Further studies involving observation of the inside of fresh leaves
208 with high vacuum SEM may also provide useful information on the origin of crystals. Small,
209 disorganized crystals may be identified as artefacts of the effect of vacuum, while large euhedral single
210 crystals present in specific cell types may be indicative of in vivo formation (e.g. Weiner et al. 2021).

211

212 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

213 All the authors developed the hypotheses, discussed the results and wrote the manuscript; AC, SP and
214 CV designed the study; AC and CV analysed data; AC led the manuscript writing.

215

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222

223 DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

224 The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon
225 reasonable request.

226

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- 297

298 FIGURE CAPTIONS

299 Figure 1: Gypsum crystals inside the leaf mesophyll cells of *Ononis tridentata* L., a gypsum endemic
300 species in the Mediterranean region. On the right side, XRD measurements taken at point (1). The
301 micrograph was taken by a FE-SEM coupled to an X-Ray Diffractometer (Carl Zeiss MERLIN™) at
302 the Analytical Services of the University of Zaragoza. Leaf samples had been collected in the field,
303 fixed in 2.5 % (v/v) glutaraldehyde in Sodium Phosphate Buffer (0.03 M, pH 7.2) for 24 hours, sliced
304 with a razor blade under the stereomicroscope, sequentially dehydrated in increasing concentrations of
305 acetone until 100%, CO₂ critical-point dried (Critical Point Dryer CPD7501 Poloron), mounted in
306 SEM stubs and Palladium-Gold coated (Sputter Coater SP7610 Poloron) prior to observation.

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308

309 Figure 2: Powder X-ray diffractograms of *Gypsophila struthium* (A, GySt), *Helianthemum squamatum*
310 (B, HeSq), *Ononis tridentata* (C, OnTr). Red lines are fresh entire leaves, and blue lines are the same
311 leaves after being dried. Crystal peaks are marked and identified. Similar X-ray diffractograms were
312 seen in four more replicates per species and treatment (see Supplementary files).

313

314

315 Figure 3: Powder X-ray diffractograms of *Gypsophila struthium* (A, GySt), *Helianthemum squamatum*
316 (B, HeSq), *Ononis tridentata* (C, OnTr). Red lines are fresh cut leaves, and blue lines are the same
317 leaves after being dried. Crystal peaks are marked and identified. Similar X-ray diffractograms were
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